

Household Food Collection CRF

#	Question	Variable
1	Today's date	DD/MM/YYYY
2	Household ID	
3	Visit	Baseline Visit Follow-up Visit 1 Follow-up Visit 2 Follow-up Visit 3
4	Sample ID	
5	Sample Type	Fruit (go to 5a) Vegetable (go to 5b) Other (specify)
5a	If fruit, what was it?	Apple Banana Pear Berry Mango Watermelon Pineapple Jackfruit Citrus fruit (e.g. orange, lemon) Tomato Masau fruit Malambe fruit Other (specify)
5b	If vegetable, what was it?	Green leafy vegetable Salad vegetable Other (specify)
6	Was the food cooked	Yes No
<p><i>You have completed data collection for this food sample.</i></p> <p><i>Please obtain 2 food samples per household where possible.</i></p>		
7	Staff signature	
8	Time and Date	MM:HH DD/MM/YYYY